

DEVELOPMENT OF LINGUISTIC COMPETENCE OF ENGLISH TEACHERS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS BASED ON SMART TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. In this article, in the era of digital technologies and innovations, several methods of developing linguistic competences of future English language teachers based on smart technologies and effective teaching of English, modern educational technologies used in language and its learning are discussed. is conducted.

Key words: Digital technology, innovative, technologies, methodology, modern world, pedagogical innovation;

Digital literacy is the set of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for life in the modern world, to use digital technologies and Internet resources safely and effectively. Creating and maintaining dynamic online profiles is the ability to manage large and complex online social networks.

Digital literacy refers to a core set of knowledge, skills, and attitudes that enable a person to effectively solve problems in a digital environment.

Digital Literacy Components:

- Information literacy
- Knowledge about the characteristics of information and its various sources
- Skills to find and compare relevant information
- Responding to the benefits and harms of information
- Computer literacy
- Knowledge of computer equipment and its functions
- Computer and similar device usage skills;

The task of the teacher is to create conditions for practical mastery of the language for each student, to choose such teaching methods that allow each student to demonstrate his activity and creativity. The task of the teacher is to activate the cognitive activity of the student in the process of teaching foreign languages. Modern pedagogical technologies, such as collaborative learning, project methodology, use of new information technologies, Internet resources, help to implement a person-oriented approach in the educational process, individualization of teaching taking into account the abilities of children, their level of learning and ensures differentiation. Forms of working with computer training programs in foreign language classes include: learning vocabulary; practice pronunciation; teaching dialogic and monologic speech; teaching writing; development of grammatical events.

The possibilities of using Internet resources are huge. The Global Internet makes it possible for students and teachers located anywhere in the world to get any information they need: regional geographic materials, youth news, articles from newspapers and magazines, etc.

A number of didactic problems can be solved using the Internet in English in lessons: formation of reading skills and competencies using global network materials; improving the writing ability of schoolchildren; filling students' vocabulary; formation of students' motivation to learn English. In addition, this work aims to explore the possibilities of Internet technologies to expand the horizons of schoolchildren, establish and maintain business

relations and contacts with peers in English-speaking countries. Students can take part in online tests, quizzes, contests, Olympiads, correspond with their peers in other countries, chat, videoconference, etc.

The meaningful basis of mass computerization is related to the fact that the modern computer is an effective tool for optimizing the conditions of mental work, in general, in any of its forms. The computer has one characteristic that defines its use as a tool for teaching others and as an aid in the acquisition of knowledge, and that is its inanimate nature. The machine can have a "friendly" relationship with the user and sometimes "support" him, but he will never show signs of anger and will not let you feel bored. In this sense, the use of computers is perhaps most useful in individualizing some aspects of teaching. The main goal of learning a foreign language at school is the formation of communicative competence, all other goals (education, training, development) are implemented in the process of realizing this main goal. Communicative approach includes communication training and the formation of intercultural communication skills, which are the basis of Internet activities. Without communication, the Internet has no meaning, it is an international multinational, intercultural society, whose life is based on the electronic communication of millions of people around the world, talking at the same time - in terms of the number and size of participants. the biggest conversation.

Currently, communication, interactivity, authenticity of communication, language learning in cultural context, autonomy and humanitarianism of education are given priority. These principles allow the development of intercultural competence as a component of communicative competence. The ultimate goal of foreign language teaching is to teach a free direction in a foreign language environment and the ability to respond adequately to different situations, that is, communication. Today, new methods using Internet resources are opposed to traditional foreign language teaching. To teach communication in a foreign language, you need to create real, real-life situations that stimulate the learning of the material and develop adequate behavior (that is, the so-called principle of communication authenticity). New technologies, especially the Internet, are trying to correct this error. Communicative approach is a strategy that simulates communication aimed at conscious understanding of the material and methods of working with it, creating psychological and linguistic preparation for communication. It is not particularly difficult for the user to implement a communicative approach on the Internet. A communicative task should invite students to discuss a problem or question, students not only exchange information, but also evaluate it. The main criterion that allows distinguishing this approach from other types of educational activity is that students independently choose linguistic units to form their thoughts. In the communicative approach, the use of the Internet is highly encouraged: its purpose is to interest students in learning a foreign language by accumulating and expanding their knowledge and experience.

One of the main requirements for teaching foreign languages using Internet resources is to create interaction in the lesson, which is usually called interactivity in the methodology. Interactivity is "combining, coordinating, and complementing communicative goals and resulting efforts by means of speech." By teaching the real language, the Internet helps to build speaking skills and abilities, and also ensures genuine interest and therefore effectiveness in teaching vocabulary and grammar. Interactivity not only creates real situations from life, but also forces students to give appropriate answers to them in a foreign language.

One of the technologies that provide student-centered education is the project method as a method of developing creativity, knowledge activity, and independence. The typology of projects is diverse. Projects can be divided into monoprosjects, collective, oral, concrete, written and Internet projects. In actual practice, it is often necessary to deal with research projects, mixed projects with creative, practice-oriented and informational features. Project work is a multifaceted approach to language learning, covering reading, listening, speaking and grammar. The project method helps to develop active independent thinking of students and directs them to joint research work. In my opinion, project-based learning teaches children to cooperate, and learning to cooperate inculcates moral values such as mutual aid and empathy, builds creativity, and activates students. In general, the inseparability of teaching and education is observed in the process of teaching the project.

In conclusion, an important pedagogical condition for the formation of creativity in teachers is to direct it to independent learning and creative thinking. In addition, special attention should be paid to the use of creative environment, specific moral and spiritual state, organizational, methodical and psychological measures among teachers. It is precisely for this reason that it determines the level of optimality of pedagogical innovations. Effectiveness as the most important sign of innovative methods is manifested only when positive achievements are made in the teacher's work. The technological, observability, and recording of results in measurements is demonstrated by evaluating new methods and methods of teaching. The important aspect of this measure is manifested in the unity of the formation of a person, his perception and concepts. In this regard, the innovative process can be considered as the process of bringing the scientific idea to the stage of practical use and implementing changes in the social and pedagogical environment. The activity that ensures the transformation of ideas into innovation and forms the management system of this process is an innovative activity. There is another distinctive feature of the development stages of the innovation process. The creative application of pedagogical innovations in pedagogical experience is manifested at the initial stage of the work of individual teachers.

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